

A Quantitative Study of the Influence of Anisotropy on the Bending Deformation of Laminates

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to assess and quantify the influence of anisotropy on the mechanical behaviour of laminates. Anisotropy is measured with the *degree of anisotropy* introduced from polar representation of tensors. Various laminates, with controlled and random stacking sequences, were analysed under typical bending conditions using different finite elements. The results were compared using a completely isotropic material as reference. They show that the influence of anisotropy on deformation variables (deflections, rotations and curvatures) is small or very small when the degree of anisotropy is small.

KEY WORDS: Composite laminated plate; Bending deformation; Finite element; Stacking sequences; Degree of anisotropy; Isotropy.

INTRODUCTION

The classical laminated plate theory and its extensions, with the use of finite elements, provide a convenient tool for the analysis of composite structures already designed. However, no design rules can be easily based on the results of such analysis process, due to the complex behaviour of the laminated structures and the large number of parameters involved. The purpose of this work was to contribute to the design methodology by investigating and assessing the influence of anisotropy on mechanical

behaviour. The polar representation of anisotropic properties was selected as a convenient tool for the study. Numerical finite element simulations of bending of various laminated plates were used. In view of the preliminary results, it was retained to concentrate on the deformation variables: deflection, rotations and curvatures. The general trends observed are that the influence of anisotropy on these variables may be small or very small.

1. POLAR REPRESENTATION METHOD

This method was developed by Verchery and co-workers (1)-(4). It uses representation of tensors by parameters so called *polar components*. For plane elastic stiffness, six parameters are required. These polar components give the key to compare various anisotropic materials together, using a relative deviation defined from the polar components of the materials to be compared. This relative deviation is convenient for many applications, among which two are used in the present work.

1.1 Degree of anisotropy A special application of the relative deviation is the definition of the degree of anisotropy of a material. It is defined as the relative deviation in stiffness between the material and its isotropic part (the isotropic part of a material should be defined from polar components, but for a laminate, it can be more simply seen as the material with the in-plane property of a quasi-isotropic laminate made with this material). The degree of anisotropy so defined is positive and always less than 1.

1.2 Nearly isotropic and nearly quasi-homogeneous materials A material is said to be nearly isotropic if its relative deviation with its isotropic part is sufficiently small. Similarly, a laminated material is said to be nearly quasi-homogeneous if the relative deviation between its normalized in-plane and bending stiffnesses is sufficiently small.

2. FINITE ELEMENT USED

Three types of plate finite elements were selected to assess the influence of the laminate constitution on the bending behaviour. All these elements have 5 degrees of freedom per node: 3 displacements u, v, w and two rotations θ_x and θ_y . According to the element type, the rotations are independent variables or related to the deflection. Further, all these elements were extended to take into account the complete laminate behaviour (anisotropy and coupling) (5).

2.1 Ahmad-type plate element This 8-node quadrilateral finite element (Figure 1) is based on the first-order shear deformation plate theory (Mindlin plate theory) (6).

Figure 1. Ahmad-type plate finite element with 40 d.o.f.

2.2 Discrete Kirchhoff Quadrilateral (DKQ) element This 4-node quadrilateral element (7) is derived using the so-called *discrete Kirchhoff hypothesis* technique. The transverse shear effect is neglected

Figure 2. DKQ plate finite element with 20 d.o.f.

2.3 Discrete Shear Triangular (DST) element This 3-node triangular element is based on the so-called *discrete shear hypothesis*, recently developed (8) to extend the discrete Kirchhoff hypothesis in order to incorporate transverse shear effects.

Figure 3. DST plate finite element with 15 d.o.f.

3. MATERIALS USED

The ply used to build the laminates in all the study is an orthotropic material made of an epoxy resin reinforced with unidirectional graphite fibers, with the following engineering constants:

E_{11}	= 175	GPa	E_{22}	= 7	GPa
G_{12}	= 3.5	GPa	G_{23}	= 1.4	GPa
G_{13}	= 3.5	GPa	ν_{12}	= 0.25	

Two categories of multi-layer composite plates are used in this work: laminates with i) controlled, and ii) random stacking sequences.

3.1 Controlled stacking sequences laminated plates Three types of stacking sequences configurations are considered:

3.1.1 Unidirectional laminates

3.1.2 Cross-ply laminates The symmetric stacking sequences are:

$$[[0/90/0/90/0/90/0/90/0]_r]_s$$

in which r is a repetition index, equal to 1 and 10 (angles in degrees). Figure 4 show the variation with the direction of in-plane and bending equivalent Young's moduli \bar{E} and \tilde{E} for $r = 1$ and 10. For $r = 4$ and more, the laminate is nearly quasi-homogeneous (within less than 1.25 %).

Figure 4 : Variation with the angle of the in-plane \bar{E} and bending \tilde{E} Young's moduli for cross-ply with $r=1$ and $r=10$ respectively.

3.1.3 Quasi-isotropic laminates The selected stacking sequences are :

$$[60/-60/0/-60/0/60/0/60/-60]_r \quad \text{and} \quad [[0/45/90/-45]_p]_s$$

in which r and p are the repetition indices, equal to 1, 4 and 2, 20 respectively. Figure 5 and 6 show the variation with the angle of the in-plane and bending equivalent Young moduli \bar{E} and \tilde{E} for different values of r and p . It can be seen that for $r \geq 4$ the first laminate is nearly isotropic, whereas, for the second, the evolution towards the isotropy is much slower.

Figure 5 : Variation with angle of the in-plane \bar{E} and bending \tilde{E} Young's moduli for a quasi-isotropic material ($[0/\pm 60]$ for $r = 1$ and 4).

Figure 6 : Variation with angle of the in-plane \bar{E} and bending \tilde{E} Young's moduli for a quasi-isotropic material ($[0/\pm 45/90]$ with $p = 2$ and 20).

3.2 Random stacking sequences laminated plates

Various

18-ply symmetric laminates were selected at random with a uniform distribution of the angles (9). A sample of 20 random sequences was studied. It was found that the degree of anisotropy varies from 13% to 54%. The extreme cases are shown below and graphically illustrated in Figure 7.

[35/8/65/140/118/128/75/126/86/132/74/15/7/2/75/141/41/27] $\epsilon = 13\%$

[82/61/40/163/53/169/61/79/63/155/65/69/108/109/5/12/107/57] $\epsilon = 54\%$

Figure 7 show the variation with the angle of the in-plane and bending normalized stiffnesses for these two random cases. The behaviour of the other groups lies between these two extreme cases.

Figure 7 : Variation with the angle of the in-plane of the in-plane \bar{E} and bending \bar{E} Young's moduli for the two extreme random cases.

4. APPLICATION EXAMPLES

A thin square plate (side = 1800 mm, thickness = 9 mm) was investigated. We studied two types of boundary and loading conditions : i) clamped with uniform pressure, and ii) mixed (clamped, simply supported and free boundaries) with concentrated load. Figure 8 shows the meshes used.

Figure 8. Meshes used for the clamped and mixed cases: (a) for DKQ and Ahmad, (b) for DST and (c) for DKQ, ● node 42 ○ node 65 □ node 81.

First, the study assessed the influence of the elements, boundary and loading conditions. Then we investigated the effects on deflection, rotations and curvatures using different types of materials, limiting to the clamped case under uniform pressure with mesh (a) and DKQ elements. These results are compared with the values obtained for an isotropic homogeneous material (defined from the quasi-isotropic case) which is taken as a reference. Specially the relative deviation $(W-W_{iso})/W_{iso}$ on the deflection is used, and plotted against the degree of anisotropy.

4.1 Element comparison The deflection at the center of the clamped plate is given in Table 1 for different types of elements in the case of a uniform load (1000 Pa) and the $[0/\pm 60]$ quasi-isotropic sequences. From the results in this table, it can be seen that the deflection obtained from different types of elements is quite the same, for any value of ϵ . It can be concluded that the type of element has no significant influence on the parameters studied. Consequently, in the following, the D.K.Q element has been used.

Aniso. Degree %	D.S.T	Ahmad	D.K.Q
34	3.103	3.092	3.136
8.5	3.105	3.093	3.135
2.5	3.103	3.095	3.132
0.34	3.103	3.096	3.131
0.0	3.103	3.057	3.131

TABLE 1: Central deflection in mm for a clamped uniformly loaded square plate with various quasi-isotropic materials $[0/\pm 60]$.

4.2 Influence of boundary and loading conditions To assess the influence of the boundary and loading conditions, a mixed condition case was also studied and its results were examined in different manners. This is exemplified in Table 2, which shows that the general trends are the same as with the clamped plate under uniform load. A more complete analysis, including effects on rotations and curvatures, has confirmed that the boundary and loading conditions have little influence (9). Consequently, the clamped plate under uniform loading is retained in the following.

Aniso. Degree %	W_{42}	W_{65}	W_{81}
34	7.37	2.54	16.86
8.5	6.30	2.38	15.58
2.5	6.13	2.35	15.34
0.34	6.08	2.35	15.28
Isotropic	6.08	2.35	15.26

TABLE 2: Deflection in mm for the square plate with mixed boundary conditions under concentrated load at node 42 (see Figure 8-c).

4.3 Influence of anisotropy on the deflection and curvatures

More than 30 materials configurations were analysed for the square clamped plate under uniform pressure. The results were analysed in order to assess the influence of anisotropy. To our outmost surprise, we observed rather small differences on the deformation variables (deflection, rotations, and curvatures). As no single quantity can represent the difference in the fields of deformation, we made comparison at selected points or lines. The following presents some typical results and conclusions.

4.3.1 Deflection Figures 6 to 10 give the relative deviation of the deflection w at different points of the plate versus the degree of anisotropy ϵ or the deflection along the symmetry axis of the plate, for controlled and random stacking sequences. All the results in these figures show that the influence of anisotropy on the deflection is always in the range of $\pm 10\%$ with reference to the deflection for the isotropic case, except in the case of unidirectional laminate for which the central deflection is about 13% in excess.

Figure 6. The relative deviation in deflection (in percent) for controlled sequences at node 58.

Figure 7. The relative deviation in deflection (in percent) for random sequences at node 58.

Figure 8. The deflection along the symmetry axis (controlled sequences).

Figure 9. The deflection along the symmetry axis for 3 examples of random sequences compared to the isotropic case.

Fig 10. The relative deviation in deflection (in percent) for controlled and random sequences at the plate center.

4.3.2 Curvatures The same study was done for the curvatures. Tables 3 and 4 give the variation of the curvatures (K_{xx} , K_{yy} , and K_{xy}) at different points of the plate versus the degree of anisotropy ϵ for controlled and random stacking sequences. All the results in these tables show that the influence of anisotropy on the curvatures is more important than on the deflection, but generally remains small.

Aniso. Degree	Kxx		Kyy		Kxy	
	node 58	center	node 58	center	node 58	center
iso.	-4.83	-13.51	-0.52	-13.51	9.85	0.00
0.34	-4.82	-13.50	-0.51	-13.52	9.85	0.00
2.1	-4.81	-13.43	-0.47	-13.55	9.81	0.00
8.5	-4.75	-13.18	-0.33	-13.67	9.66	0.00
34	-4.42	-11.66	+0.12	-14.04	8.76	0.00

TABLE 3: Curvatures at center and node 58 for the uniformly loaded clamped plate for quasi-isotropic material[0/±60].

Aniso. Degree	Kxx		Kyy		Kxy	
	node 58	center	node 58	center	node 58	center
iso.	-4.83	-13.51	-0.52	-13.51	09.85	0.00
12.95	-4.75	-13.25	-0.62	-13.72	09.56	0.00
29.75	-5.12	-16.25	-1.34	-14.94	10.35	0.00
33.44	-5.10	-09.83	-1.78	-07.61	10.58	0.00
54.29	-5.75	-29.45	+0.97	-27.90	09.08	0.00

TABLE 4: Curvatures at node 58 and center for the uniformly loaded clamped plate for four random sequences.

CONCLUSION

This work represents an original attempt to quantify the influence of anisotropy on the bending of laminated plates. The deflection, rotations and curvatures of the plates were studied as functions of the degree of anisotropy for different controlled and random stacking sequences. First, it was shown that the influence of the types of finite elements and boundary and loading conditions were negligible. Surprisingly, our investigation shows that the effect of laminate anisotropy is rather small on the deflection variables: for example the deviation on the deflections is less than 2% up to values of 30% of the degree of anisotropy; the influence on the rotations and the curvatures is greater but remains small. Of course, these conclusions cannot be extended to the distribution of forces variables, such as moments, shear forces and

specially stresses in the laminas. However, the small variations from the isotropic case observed in this study seem to open a way for the use of all the results available on classical isotropic structures in the preliminary design of laminates.

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